

Structural Analysis and Understanding of Graphical Layouts in Documents

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Abstract

In computer vision applied to document understanding, layout is a fundamental component. Many document categories usually follow a (pseudo) structural formalism that described a document as a valid instance of a given syntax. Examples exist in different categories: invoices, forms, graphical diagrams, scientific articles and so on. In all these cases, the constituent terms are not only recognized individually as a result of an OCR engine, but, especially when the image interpretation conveys semantic labeling (Named Entity Recognition), the geometric context where they appear plays a fundamental role. Layout information in the form of graphical elements (tables, figures, paragraphs etc.) play a vital role in conveying rich and valuable information contained in a document. In this work, we present novel end-to-end deep learning based object detection frameworks using different public benchmark datasets to localize and structurally understand complex graphical layouts in document images. We also try to investigate the concept of transfer learning and domain adaptation to handle the scarcity of labeled training data for the object detection task in document images. Performance analysis and extensive experiments has been carried out on the benchmark datasets like PubLayNet, ICDAR-POD 2017 and ICDAR-RDCL 2019 to study the impact of these concepts and derive significant insight. Finally, we have proposed an automated generative model using Graph Neural Networks(GNNs) to generate synthetic data that can be used to train document interpretation systems, in this case, specially in digital mailroom applications. It is interesting to note that our synthetic graph generation model also becomes the first baseline approach experimented on administrative document images, in this case, invoices. Additionally, a novel dataset derived from RVL-CDIP invoice data has been also contributed to the community.

Index Terms

Document object detection; graphical layout understanding; transfer learning; domain adaptation; structural pattern recognition; graph neural networks; synthetic data generation; document layout generation

I. INTRODUCTION

IN this chapter we introduce the context and motivation of this thesis related to computer vision and pattern recognition. In particular, the main challenges in document image analysis has been discussed. Moreover, we also highlighted the main objectives and contributions of this work. Finally, we outline the different modules and organization of the dissertation.

A. Setting the Context

Visual perception is one of the most fundamental senses for humans and others animals. It is the power of vision that enables us(humans) to interact with the environment. We try and pick up an object or avoid getting collided with some object on our path or even try to recognise people by their faces - for all these tasks object localization and recognition is extremely essential. What is really amazing is how effortlessly we process these tasks in our brain with visual perception! We never think about these basic processing steps actively with our grey matter. But these tasks which seem so facile for our brain can actually pose a serious challenge to most artificially intelligent systems like robots which tend to process image content. Existing algorithms in computer vision literature tend to just process a small subset of tasks that are important for visual understanding of different images. Also they require huge computational resources and runtime to perform these tasks with reasonable efficiency. To actually reproduce the human visual perception abilities in Intelligent Systems require combining these algorithms and running them in real time with the hardware resources available in store. A small step towards this goal in computer vision is by training a neural network model to learn the essential image components (features) that are significant and interesting to human observers to search for a definite object category. This small knowledge realistically speeds up the "object search" in them. Object detection in Computer Vision has grown immensely in recent years with end-to-end trainable models deployed with deep CNNs. In this work we have investigated its extensive application to Document Image Analysis and Recognition(DIAR) systems to solve some very relevant specific tasks.

The inception of the document analysis field dates back to the 1960s where Document Image Analysis and Recognition (DIAR) was designated as "To recognise the text and graphical components of a document and to extract information". A really well-known problem is the Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) which has been a popular computer vision benchmark task for evaluating Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, in most cases supervised classifiers. Character recognition and word recognition problems have been given much more importance over the years. Yet, there are other tasks such as document

preprocessing [1] [2], layout analysis [3] [4], character segmentation [5] [6], and signature verification [7] [8] that benefited so much from extremely robust state-of-the-art machine learning techniques practised in recent years. The variability and diversity of complex layouts and graphical entities in digital mailroom documents prevent us from tackling each problem separately, and that such specificity has been a great barrier towards deriving off-the-shelf document analysis solutions, usable by non-specialists. Apparently, OCR-based engines are the most widely recognized products in this research community. For instance, imagine a business firm having thousands of documents to process, analyze, and transform in order to carry out day-to-day operations. Examples of such documents might include receipts, invoices, forms, statements, contracts, and many more pieces of data which is highly unstructured or semi-structured, and it's really important to be able to quickly analyze and understand the information embedded within the unevenly structured data in these cases. In most of these DIAR applications the document content has been broadly classified into two structural entities: the (1) physical and the (2) logical structural entities. While the physical structure describes the visual aspect of the document by representing the specific objects and their mutual positions, the logical structure assigns a definite meaning to each of these objects. This meaning is precisely referred to as 'semantic knowledge' in context to computer vision and object detection.

B. Motivation and Challenges

With the rapid increase in usage of digital documents over the years, the need for automated methods for extraction and retrieval of information has become a necessity. Manual approaches are no longer a feasible option. There has been tools and applications in recent times to convert these digital documents into process-able entities. It has been observed that graphical page elements such as tables, figures, paragraphs, equations can indeed play a vital role in understanding and extracting information from these documents. Document Object Detection(DOD) is the fundamental task of automatically modelling a document page into its structural and logical graphic entities for its application to solve a number of document image analysis tasks. These specific tasks range from document content understanding, document structural and syntactic analysis [9] [10] [11] and so on. A document structure cannot be explicitly encoded by the two most popular document formats, images and PDFs. While images encode pixels, PDFs encode vector, raster and text marker information. Therefore, detection of graphical elements and structural objects for digitally generated documents has emerged as a challenging and interesting problem in the recent years. The problem more specifically involves the task of visually conveying messages by using different semantic entities of documents that involve text, images and symbolic information. The placement and sizing of graphic objects (tables, figures, logos etc.) describe the principal layout structure in documents. Layouts play a significant role in dictating the reader's attention and hence, the order by which it conveys the information. Variations in document layouts can often change the hierarchy and narrative of the information. In this work, we have therefore focused on detecting and recognizing graphical objects and deducing their spatial and structural relationships to solve the problem of understanding document layouts for information extraction.

Recent advances in object detection for natural scene images [12] [13] has captured a lot of attention. Our problem to detect graphical objects and understand layouts in documents is conceptually quite similar. But the large domain discrepancies in document images make it quite challenging to apply in this scenario as compared to natural scene images. The diversity in aspect ratio and scale of graphical objects and named entities in documents are far more significant as compared to that in natural scene objects. For example, in case of scientific articles, tables may occupy most part of a page, logos or figures may appear on any side of the page column width while lines of text or paragraphs can have extreme aspect ratio. This inter-class variance in the structure of graphical layouts in documents makes its detection quite difficult. Rule-based systems [14] [15] [16] [17] used before the advent of deep learning considerably fail to detect these document objects in such variable test case scenarios. In recent years, deep Convolutional Neural Networks(CNNs) [18] [19] have been able to create a major improvement in detection performances for such diverse graphical objects. But there has also emerged some crucial research questions that requires attention.

Most of these deep CNN-based methods generally try to deduct the visual differences between the object classes: while the visual characteristics of certain graphical elements(e.g. plots, charts) differ conspicuously from text, the same cannot be said for tables, where the major differences from the surrounding content lie mostly stored in the layout information and its context. Also, trying to train these deep CNN models from scratch may be quite impractical due to the requirement of a huge amount of data and also the need of appropriately annotated document datasets, which are scarcely available in the community. The key reason may be most of these documents (administrative documents, for example) contain sensitive information(identity name, bank details, health information and so on) and are not publicly released by the government agencies or business firms to be used in cloud services. Hence, there is an important need to generate synthetic data samples that can encode the structural information of the real data and can be used during training to transfer enough knowledge to our model. This specific task has been defined as Document Layout Generation(DLG) in our work.

C. Objectives and Contributions of this thesis

In this thesis, we have tried to come up with robust and powerful solutions to answer the challenges and research questions asked in the above subsection. The main objective of this thesis is to develop an end-to-end system to effectively capture the structural content information of graphical object layouts in document collections.

In summary, the main contributions of this work are: (1) An **end-to-end** trainable Document Object Detection(DOD) model has been proposed to detect all kinds of page object categories. Performances of this model has been evaluated and compared with existing state-of-the-art methods on two significant benchmark datasets in the document analysis community : the ICDAR-POD-2017 [20] and PubLayNet [21]. (2) To solve the **scarcity of enough annotated data** for training, we have explored the concept of transfer learning and domain adaptation for detecting graphical object layouts in documents. Experiments were conducted with public benchmark document datasets by leveraging labeled data in the source domain and unlabeled data in target domain to train a detector for the target domain. (3) A new baseline approach to **generate synthetic data** has been introduced using Graph Neural Networks(GNNs) where we render data in the form of diverse graphs that can match the structural characteristics of a target dataset.(4) A **novel dataset** consisting of 500 invoice pages from RVL-CDIP [22] has been contributed with ground truth for both DOD and document layout generation(DLG) tasks.

D. Organization

The rest of the dissertation has been organized as follows: Section II reviews the state-of-the-art approaches in the field, whereas Section III describes the proposed model frameworks for the specific tasks(DOD and DLG), section IV describes the experimental setup for the tasks, section V evaluates our approaches and discusses our obtained results on different datasets and section VI draws conclusions and outlines future research lines.

II. RELATED WORK

Automatic information extraction from the digital documents require the detection and understanding of graphical objects such as tables, figures, equations, etc. A good number of researchers have contributed to localize various page objects and layout analysis on the different types of documents. Based on this schema, we describe the state-of-the-art under different subsections as listed below:

A. Traditional rule-based approaches

Prior to the deep learning era, most of the traditional approaches [14] [15] [16] [17] solved the table detection problem in documents by assuming table structures and using the prior knowledge on the properties of objects and extracting them by analyzing tokens from documents. The work done by Tupaj *et. al.* [15] was one of the first to address a solution by developing an Optical Character Recognition(OCR) based table recognition system by initially identifying a potential table region. Then they used keyword analysis to determine the header which is interpreted as the starting line of the table and then vertical and horizontal passes in a page would help to identify white space regions between the cells of the table region. This rule-based approach heavily relies on keyword analysis for searching table headers and also prior assumption of table structures. Shafait *et. al.* [17] improved further this rule-based approach by applying table spotting with tab-spaces and predicting and removing false alarms to enhance performance in more variable layout structures. Fang *et. al.* [16] used separator mining technique that could identify visual separators of cells and help to analyze more clearly the page layout and detect the table from PDF documents with greater accuracy. Chen *et. al.* [14] used Support Vector Machines (SVM) classifier in scanned handwritten text documents to separate the text line components and then determining the correlation between adjacent text lines which may be part of the table. The approach resulted in solving the page decomposition problem with dynamic programming and surpassed the performances of previous methods. But the key disadvantage of all these rule-based approaches was they failed to generate good results in tables with variable layout structures. The structure and type of the table were taken as inherent assumptions for using these segmentation based approaches. This incensed the need for data driven approaches using deep CNN's in the document analysis community for providing a more robust solution to solve its tasks.

B. Document Object Detection with Deep Learning approaches

With the advent of deep CNN's, the performance of object detection tasks in computer vision has achieved manifolds. It is always recommended to have a strong backbone feature extractor for building accurate detection models. In recent state-of-the-art custom object detection networks are broadly classified into two different categories: two-stage and one-stage. Faster-RCNN (FRCNN) [13] is one of the most popular two-stage detectors used in recent years for object detection tasks. It generates coarse-grained object proposals using a Region Proposal Network (RPN) module in the first stage. These region proposals and refined features are then fed to the Classification module in the second and final stage. In this work, FRCNN has been used as a base detector but our work can be applicable to other two-stage and one-stage detectors like SSD [23], YOLO [18] and Retinanet [24]. All these base detectors have been pre-trained on ImageNet [25] and then needs to be fine-tuned again on a large number of annotated bounding box proposals, in our case, on document images.

In recent years deep CNNs have proved to be quite effective and has been explored by quite a number of research groups in document object analysis. Hao *et. al.* [26] have used them for detecting tables in PDF documents by generating region proposals with table-like structures in document pages and then classifying them into table or non-table entities using a CNN. But the key drawback in rule-based segmentation approaches was not totally overcome. Schreiber *et. al.* [9] then devised a very

standard deep learning approach called DeepDeSRT for table detection and structure recognition, where no prior knowledge or assumption about table structures was necessary. In contrast to the existing table detection and structure recognition approaches that were only applicable for processing PDFs, DeepDeSRT helped processing document images too which made it quite robust to process born-digital images as well as even harder problems, e.g. scanned documents. They applied fine-tuning on existing Faster-RCNN with emphasis on two different backbones for table detection task: ZFNet [27] and VGG16 [28]. Gilani [29] improved the model performance further for table detection without changing the model backbones used by Schreiber *et. al.* [9]. They introduced a new pre-processing unit where they applied image transformation on the samples using a stack of 3 different distance transformed layers before feeding them to the Faster-RCNN. He *et. al.* [30] used a two-stage system architecture for detecting table and figures. The class label for every pixel is predicted using a multi-scale and multi-task Fully Convolutional Neural Networks(FCNN) in the first stage of the model framework. The next stage is the region proposal network where certain heuristic rules are applied on these pixel-wise class predictions to get the object bounding boxes (region proposals). Gao *et. al.* devised an end-to-end approach to detect mathematical formulas using a combination of CNNs and RNNs (Recurrent Neural Networks) to use both character and vision features. They extracted the meta-data information from the PDF files before passing them to the feature extraction network. To extend the problem to detect multiple graphical objects jointly, Gao *et. al.* [20] organized a competition in the 2017 edition of the International Conference in Document Analysis and Recognition(ICDAR) and proposed a baseline for multi-object scenario. In this work we have also used this dataset to test and evaluate our model performance. Yi *et. al.* [31] redesigned the common CNN object detection approach with a newly devised training strategy, network structure and used a dynamic programming algorithm to prevent the usage of Non Maximal Suppression(NMS) for their model training. Li *et. al.* [32] used a deep structure prediction to obtain primitive region proposals from every column region. Then these primitive proposals are clustered and merged with Conditional Random Field (CRF) based graphical models that can be used to integrate both contextual and local information. This helped them achieve state-of-the-art performance on the ICDAR-POD-2017 [20] dataset.

C. Geometric Deep Learning

Geometric deep learning [33] [34] is a trending field in deep learning nowadays where the application of neural networks has been extended to non-Euclidean domains, such as graphs and manifolds. In order to refer to neural networks applied to these kind of graph-structures, the term Graph Neural Networks [35] (GNN) was coined.

The GNN methods help to learn representations at the node, edge and graph level considering the underlying topological information. Based on the fundamental architecture, GNN methods can be aptly divided into two categories: spatial and spectral methods. Spatial methods extend the idea of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for images and define a set of operations involving the local neighbourhood to compute a new representation [36] [37]. On the other hand, spectral methods use the knowledge of spectral graph theory [38] and consider graph Laplacians for defining convolution operations in graph domain [33] [34]. Gilmer et al. [39] generalized both the domains of GNN, and defined their approach in terms of a Neural Message Passing (NMP) pipeline. These fundamental architectures have been further extended to new tasks involving graphs, such as the generative variational graph autoencoder [40], learning graph edit distance between a pair of graphs [41], graph matching [42] etc.

D. Document Layout Analysis and Generation

The study and analysis of the structural properties and relations between entities in documents is a fundamental challenge in the field of information retrieval. Although local tasks like the Optical Character Recognition (OCR) have been addressed with a considerably high model performance, the global and highly variable nature of document layouts has made their analysis some what more ambiguous. Previous works on structural document analysis mostly relied on the different kinds of specifically devised methods and applications (e.g., [43], [44], [45], [46]). Recent works have shown that deep learning based approaches have significantly improved the performance of these models in quality. A very standard approach in this regard was proposed by Yang et al. [47] which uses a joint visual and textual representation in a multimodal way of understanding, viewing the layout analysis as a pixel-wise segmentation task. But such modern deep learning based approaches typically require a very heavy amount of high-quality training data, that often calls for suitable methods to synthetically generate documents with real-looking layout [48] and content [49]. Our work actually focuses on the direction of research on synthetic layout generation, showing that our generated synthetic data can be extremely beneficial to augment training data for document analysis tasks.

Preserving the reliable representation of layouts has shown to be very useful in various graphical design contexts, which typically involve highly structured and content-rich objects. One such recent intuitive understanding was established by Li et al. [48] in their LayoutGAN, which aims to generate realistic document layouts using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) with a wireframe rendering layer. Zheng et. al. [50] used a GAN-based approach to generate document layouts but their work focused mainly on content aware generation, that primarily uses the content of the document as an additional prior. To use more highly structured object generation, it is very important to focus operate on the low dimensional vectors unlike CNN's. Hence, in the most recent literature, Patil et. al. [51] has come up with a solution called 'READ' that can make use of this highly structured positional information along with content to generate document layouts. They have used recursive neural networks

which operate on the low dimensional vectors and employ two-layer perceptrons to merge any two vectors, which make them computationally cheaper and help them train with fewer samples. The recursive neural networks are coupled with Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) in their resulting model architecture and provides state-of-the-art results for generating synthetic layouts for 2D documents. They have also introduced a novel metric for measuring document similarity, called DocSim, and used this metric to show the novelty and diversity of the generated layouts. Figure 1 shows an example of how they make use of relational information between the layouts on an example document.

Fig. 1: **The READ framework:** Exploratory layout extraction strategy used in a document

Using geometric relations between the different entities in documents can actually help to preserve the structural information along with the content as seen in the work by Riba et. al. on table detection in invoice documents using GNNs. Figure 7 clearly illustrates how they have used GNNs to capture the geometrical structure of an invoice and using this knowledge can help us to generate more realistic synthetic samples for training. Traditional generative models for graphs [52] are usually hand-crafted to model a particular family of graphs, and thus they do not have the capacity to directly learn the generative model from observed data. To find a solution, one such graph-based generative model using GNNs was proposed by You et. al. [53] on molecular data generation. They used sequential generation with Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) on top of graph based representations and get state-of-the-art results on molecular data generation. But there has not been any substantial work in the literature which has applied such graph-based generative models for document layout analysis tasks. In this context, it is indeed a challenging problem which we tackle in our master dissertation. As case study, we will work in the context of administrative documents, primarily focusing on invoices. Automated generation of layouts will allow to generate synthetic data (invoices) that can be used to train document interpretation systems, in this case, in digital mail room applications.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section presents a complete analysis of the proposed methods that are adapted for this work inspired by the end-to-end trainable state-of-the-art object detection algorithms in computer vision [13] [54]. Detection of the graphical objects in documents that includes tables, figures, paragraphs, equations etc. is conceptually a similar problem to object detection in natural scene images. Natural scene objects have visual cues, whose features can be extracted using a CNN. Similarly, in document images, graphical objects can be analyzed with the special power of CNN's. The alluring performances of powerful CNN architecture models like Faster-RCNN and Mask-RCNN on PASCAL VOC [55] and MS-COCO [56] have inspired to us to adapt these already developed frameworks to understanding document structure and detecting the graphical entities. The most challenging task in the DOD domain is the lack of training data, as these end-to-end trainable deep CNNs require large chunks of them. Hence, we decided to explore the concepts transfer learning and domain adaptation for this work. Testing the abilities of Faster-RCNN and Mask-RCNN in DOD is one of the key tasks we performed in the first phase of our work. The performances of ImageNet [25] and COCO [56] pre-trained models have been used as the backbone of our proposed framework.

Besides this, we have also proposed a novel approach in this work to generate synthetic layouts in document images using a GNN framework. Qualitative and quantitative experiments have been demonstrated conducted on a novel dataset that we have contributed in this work which is actually a subset taken from the popular RVLCDIP document database [22].

We divide this section into the following subsections: a review of the System Architecture for both models - DOD and DLG and then their Implementation details accordingly.

Fig. 2: **Proposed DOD framework:** The model takes the input image and generate the feature map, the Resnet50 with FPN backbone generates the region proposals based on the feature map and a Box Head for tightening the bounding box.

A. Proposed method for DOD

In the first part of this subsection, we have discussed about the system architecture implemented for the DOD task. Taking inspiration from models like FasterRCNN and MaskRCNN that have been already successfully implemented for detecting objects in natural scene images, we have adapted and designed our own multi-task network for detecting multiple graphical objects in DOD domain as shown in Figure 2. To understand it better, we have analyzed the proposed framework in three different blocks as described below:

1) *Backbone with Feature Pyramid Networks:* Similar to previous approaches, our model also adapts a convolutional backbone for extracting image features. We have evaluated both ResNet50 [57] and VGG16 [28] backbones, for which we find that ResNet50 backbone leads to a better accuracy in performances. For example, we put an input image into the convolutional stack consisting of $res_2, res_3, res_4, res_5$ to get a feature hierarchy from the conv layers. The output of the convolutional stack is then input into a Feature Pyramid Network(FPN) which exploits the pyramidal feature hierarchy of CNNs to build a feature pyramid of high level semantics for every layer. FPN iterates from the most coarse feature map, upsamples it by a scale factor of 2 for enhancing spatial resolution and then merges it with the preceding map, that has already undergone a 1×1 convolution. The merged feature is then smoothed with 3×3 convolution to obtain the final feature map. To get a more clear overview, Figure 3 demonstrates the above defined steps with res_4 and res_5 final layers. This above iterative process outputs a feature pyramid P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5 . These form the basis of the convolutional backbone which is then sent to the rest of the model heads.

Fig. 3: **FPN Schema:** Forward process of FPN to output feature map

The feature pyramids help to extract multi-scale feature maps with different receptive fields which not only combine high spatial resolution information from early in the stack with low-resolution but also rich semantic information that is required from deeper in the stack. This rich semantic information is especially really helpful for detecting wide categories of objects in document images.

2) *Region Proposal Networks:* The Region Proposal Networks(RPN) module proposes rectangular regions, each associated with objectness score that tells whether it represents an object or not. Region proposals are extracted from all the feature pyramid

layers by the RPN. We choose 1000 'region proposal' boxes from all the predicted boxes using the predicted objectness scores at each feature level for an image and sorting the top-K scored boxes chosen and using Non-Maximal Suppression(NMS) independently on top of it.

3) *RoI Box Head*: We take the feature maps from FPN, the top 1000 proposal boxes from RPN and the ground truth input boxes and feed them to the RoI (Region of Interest) box head. The proposals higher than the IoU threshold applied during training are counted as foreground(object) and the rest as background. After re-sampling them for balance, they are sent to the RoI Pooling layer. The RoI pooling performs max-pooling operations to convert the non-uniform sized inputs to uniform feature maps as shown in given equation 1.

$$k = \left\lceil k_0 + \log_2(\sqrt{wh}/224) \right\rceil \quad (1)$$

With the rule from equation 2, a proposal box is assigned to the appropriate feature map at k th level and 224 represents the canonical box size.

The output feature vector is passed through the Fully Connected(FC) layers for two tasks: one for box-regression(reg) and second for classification loss(clf). For an image from source(training)dataset, we calculate total detection loss L_{det}^s using the ground truth bounding box as shown in equation 2:

$$L_{det}^s = L_{reg}(x^s, y^s) + L_{cls}(x^s, y^s), \quad (2)$$

Similar to Faster-RCNN, Mask-RCNN [54] also adopts a two-stage procedure. The only difference lies in the second stage where not only the mask-RCNN predicts class label and bounding-box regression but also a binary mask for each Region of Interests(RoIs). The RoIAlign layer generates a fixed size feature in this case by preserving the spatial locations, which is then passed to the two FC heads in the same way as Faster-RCNN.

B. Proposed method for DLG

Inspired from the proposed framework in 'READ' [51] for Document Layout Generation(DLG) task as already discussed under section III, we have tried to explore a new research direction in the DIAR domain using the application of GNN [34] [33]. A hierarchical and scalable framework has been designed and implemented to exploit highly powerful graph representations in semi-structured administrative documents like invoices. Every document image has been modelled as a visibility graph which is fed to our generative model to synthesize meaningful document layouts. Figure 5 resembles the task that we want to achieve in this direction. We considered a document graph whose nodes are graphical or named entities such as tables, figures, header, date etc. while the edges represent their spatial relationships. We aim to learn a distribution $p(G)$ over an undirected graph $G = (V, E)$ defined by the node set $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ and edge set $E = \{(v_i, v_j) \mid v_i, v_j \in V\}$ that has a node ordering π to map nodes to rows/columns of adjacency matrix A^π . An adjacency matrix $A_{i,j}^\pi$ under a node ordering π can be represented as $A_{i,j}^\pi = \mathbb{1}[(\pi(v_i), \pi(v_j)) \in E]$. So, in this work, we have proposed a graph generation framework applied in context to document images, that learns to generate realistic graphs by training on a representative set of graphs known as visibility graphs modelled from documents.

Fig. 4: **Graph Generation Framework**: Forward process of graph generation at inference time credited to [53]

The main idea is to represent graphs of different node orderings as sequences, and then build a generative model on top of these sequences. As illustrated in the graph generation framework in Figure 4, we decomposed the entire process into two parts: one that generates a sequence of nodes (Node-level update) and then another process that generates a sequence of edges for every new generated node (Edge-level update) which will be explained in more detail in the below subsections in a step-wise manner.

1) *Graph to Sequence mapping*: We aim to learn a distribution $p_{model}(G)$ over graphs, based on a set of observed graphs $G = (G_1, \dots, G_s)$, sampled from a data distribution $p(G)$, where each graph, may have a different set of nodes and edges. During training time instead of learning $p(G)$ directly, whose sample space is really complex to define, we instead sample node ordering π to get a set of sequences S^π as our observations and learn $p(S^\pi)$ instead. This help us to learn a model autoregressively

Fig. 5: Synthetic generation of document layouts credited to [51]

due to the S^π . At inference time, we can simply sample G directly by computing $p(G)$ without this mapping. The mapping function f_S from graphs to sequences, for a graph $G \sim p(G)$ with n nodes under node ordering π can be determined in equation 3.

$$S^\pi = f_S(G, \pi) = (S_1^\pi, \dots, S_n^\pi) \quad (3)$$

Every element S_i^π is actually an adjacency vector that represents the edges between the present node $\pi(v_i)$ and previous nodes $\pi(v_j)$ already in graph. This can be further represented by the equation 4.

$$S_i^\pi = (A_{1,i}^\pi, \dots, A_{i-1,i}^\pi)^T, \forall i \in \{2, 3, 4, \dots, n\} \quad (4)$$

2) *GRNN Framework*: As a result of the graph to sequence mapping, our next step would be to generate the adjacency matrix of a graph G by generating these adjacency vectors $A_{i,i}^\pi$ of each node in a step by step sequential process. This can output different networks with variable number of nodes, while preserving the important topological properties of the generated graph. While transforming the learning distribution from $p(G)$ to $p(S^\pi)$, we can further decompose $p(S^\pi)$ as the product of conditional distributions over the elements due to its sequential nature as shown in equation 5.

$$p(S^\pi) = \prod_{i=1}^{n+1} p(S_i^\pi | S_1^\pi, \dots, S_{i-1}^\pi) \quad (5)$$

Now to model this still complex distribution, we used recurrent neural networks(RNNs) that consist of a state-transition function and an output-function as shown in equations 6 and 7:

$$h_i = f_{\text{trans}}(h_{i-1}, S_{i-1}^\pi) \quad (6)$$

$$\theta_i = f_{\text{out}}(h_i) \quad (7)$$

h_i is a vector which encodes the updated generated graph information, S_{i-1}^π is the adjacency vector for the last updated node $i-1$ and θ_i denotes the distribution of next node's adjacency vector i.e. $S_i^\pi \sim P_{\theta_i}$. So theoretically, the proposed Graph Recurrent Neural Network(GRNN) framework utilizes a hierarchical RNN as shown in figure 4, where the first (i.e. graph-level) RNN generates nodes and update the state of the graph. The second RNN (i.e. edge-level) generates the edges of a given node. To achieve a scalable modeling, we let these networks share their weights across all the time steps i during the training phase.

3) *Learning via Breadth-First Search*: : A great insight in our proposed method is rather than learning to generate graphs with using the Breadth-First Search(BFS) node orderings, instead of random node permutations. The BFS function takes a random permutation π as input, picks $\pi(v_1)$ as starting node and appends the node neighbours into the BFS queue in an order defined by π . The modified equation for mapping function from graphs to sequences can rewritten as shown in equation 8.

$$S^\pi = f_S(G, \text{BFS}(G, \pi)) \quad (8)$$

This technique helps the model to be trained on all possible BFS orderings, instead of all possible node permutations. As the BFS function is deterministic in nature and many-to-one i.e. one same ordering can eventually map multiple permutations, it reduces number of sequences we need to consider. It also makes the learning much simpler by reducing the number of edge predictions and adding possible edges only for the nodes that are considered in the BFS queue itself.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Evaluation Measures

1) *Document Object Detection*: A common way to determine the correctness of an object proposal is Intersection over Union (IoU). We use the mean average precision (mAP) metric@intersection over union (IoU) [0.5:0.95] from the standard MS-COCO [56] for evaluating the performances of the proposed Faster-RCNN and Masked-RCNN models on the given datasets. This metric computes the average mAP over different IoU thresholds, from 0.5 to 0.95. We also use the F1 score measure to evaluate the performance of our algorithm for detecting graphical objects and comparing with other state-of-the-art algorithm performances on the ICDAR-POD-2017 dataset. All model performances have been evaluated both categorically and also with overall average scores based on Average Precision (AP) scores for each category or object.

2) *Document Layout Generation*: To evaluate the quality of generative models it requires a comparison between the generative sets of graph and the test set. We reproduced the MMD (Maximum Mean Discrepancy) measures proposed by You *et. al.* [53] where they compare the generated graphs with the test graphs based on the moment of their empirical distribution. The squared MMD between two sets of graph samples from distributions p and q and k being the associated kernel can be written as shown in equation 9.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MMD}^2(p||q) &= \mathbb{E}_{x,y \sim p}[k(x,y)] + \mathbb{E}_{x,y \sim q}[k(x,y)] \\ &\quad - 2\mathbb{E}_{x \sim p, y \sim q}[k(x,y)] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

B. Dataset Study

1) *PubLayNet [21]*: The PubLayNet dataset for Document Layout Analysis task was launched by IBM Research, Australia in the 15th International Conference for Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR2019) and provided one of the breakthrough contributions to the Document Analysis community. The size of this dataset is also comparable to established computer vision datasets, with over 360 thousand images taken from the list of 1 million PDF articles present in the PubMed Central [58] library for scientific literature. The defined sets of categories to detect in this dataset are text, title, lists, tables and figures. The dataset has been used for both training and evaluation purposes in our study and a complete summary of its object categories is shown in Table I. It is also provided with ground truth masks that actually help us to evaluate instance segmentation performance of our model.

Object Category	Training	Testing
Text	137,673	8,084
Title	36,688	1,717
Lists	4,742	435
Figures	6,760	450
Tables	5,969	437
Total samples	191,832	11,123

TABLE I: Summary of the PubLayNet dataset used for our experiments.

2) *ICDAR-POD-17 [20]*: The dataset contains 2417 English document images which have been filtered from 1500 scientific journal papers from CiteSeer publications. It resembles broad variations in object and layout styles ranging from single-column, multi-column formats with different sets of equations, figures, tables and text. The dataset was officially released in the ICDAR2017 competition on Page Object Detection (POD) with 3 general tasks: Detection of Tables, Detection of Figures, Detection of Formulae and detection of all 3 page objects together. This data has been divided into 1600 images in the training set and 817 images for evaluating our proposed models. The dataset has been used for both training and evaluation purposes in our study.

3) *ICDAR-RDCL-19 [59]*: The dataset was launched in the ICDAR2019 competition on Recognition of Documents with Complex Layouts (RDCL). It presented challenges for page segmentation, region classification, and text recognition in an end-to-end scenario. It contained a collection of 478 scanned pages from contemporary magazines and technical articles as shown in 6. Since the size of this dataset was small, we used selective data augmentation for this small dataset, we increased its total size to 3086 samples. The dataset has been used exclusively used only during training to do a cross-dataset evaluation to demonstrate transfer learning and domain adaptation to show that our models can actually produce generalized results when trained and fine-tuned on different domains.

4) *RVLCDIP Invoices*: The original RVL-CDIP [22] dataset has 400,000 document images in grayscale which are divided in 16 classes with 25,000 images per class. For our Document Layout Generation (DLG) task we have evaluated our GNN framework on selected 500 dataset samples taken from the invoice class of the RVL-CDIP, that mostly represented administrative document samples. They have been annotated with 4 regions, including table, header, address and others. A complete summary of the dataset has been shown in Table II.

Fig. 6: **ICDAR-RDCL 2019**: Reading competition for understanding complex layouts.

Total documents(train,val,test)	500(350,50,100)
Total pages	500
Total classes	4
Avg. nodes/page	90
Avg. edges/page	400

TABLE II: Summary of the RVL-CDIP invoice dataset.

C. Experimental Setup for Document Object Detection

There has been three important datasets that have been used for experimental validation of our proposed Document Object Detection(DOD) model. We have already covered a comprehensive summary of the datasets before.

1) *Preprocessing and Data Augmentation*: Before feeding the data to the model it is highly necessary to conduct pre-processing and data augmentation strategies on the training data which is quite limited. Given below are the key pre-processing techniques we performed on our data:

- The mean and standard deviation of the training images were calculated to normalize the images for every dataset before they were fed into the FasterRCNN and MaskRCNN models.
- TIFF format was causing problems in data augmentation and training on TIFF images takes 5x more time than on JPEG format images because of their huge size. Therefore, TIFF images were converted to JPEG format images.
- Selective data augmentation: To generate more data for training and to decrease bias and class imbalance, a customised function was implemented from the scratch. This function produces random translational augmented images of only those images which have minority classes in them. Using this function for data augmentation, we increased the dataset size for ICDAR-RDCL-2019 so that they can be used for training effectively. Since most part of a document image is filled with text, there are way more paragraphs and headers in compared to tables,graphs,charts or any minority label.
- The given XML annotations in ICDAR-POD-2017 [20] and ICDAR-RDCL-2019 [59] were needed to be converted to the COCO format so that they can be used for training.

2) *Training Setup*: We conducted training with our proposed Faster-RCNN and Mask-RCNN based model on the ICDAR-2017-POD and PubLayNet datasets. We resized the training images to a fixed size (600x600) before passing them through the model framework. The model has been implemented using the popular detectron2 [60] framework released by the Facebook research team for end-to-end state-of-the-art object detector models. Detectron2 is built on top of PyTorch [61] and is extremely simple and robust for model deployment. Nvidia Titan X GPU's have been utilized for all our training purposes. Pre-trained models backbones of VGG16 [28] and ResNet50 [57], trained on ImageNet [25], has been used as backbones for both Faster-RCNN and Mask-RCNN. ResNet50 backbone provided better accuracy in performance compared to VGG16, so it has been used as the standard backbone for our best model. The summary of our training parameters for the model has been shown in Table III. To fine tune, we initialize the weights on the pre-trained models and we train the "heads" layer using our dataset. We used 3x3 sliding windows in the RPN. To generate k=32 anchor boxes, we considered different anchor scales to cover almost all parts of the image. Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) with Nesterov Momentum was used with initial learning rate=0.001 and the learning rate scheduled to decay after every 15 epochs and equal to 0.1 times the previous value.

3) *Experiments with self-dataset evaluation*: The ICDAR-POD-2017 and PubLayNet datasets were used to evaluate our model performance with their own training set and compare them with existing state-of-the-art approaches used in the past on these datasets.

For the ICDAR-POD-2017 dataset, our model achieves the state-of-the-art performance compared to previous existing state-of-the-art methods like NLPR-PAL, HustVision, VisInt and FastDetectors which were submitted to the ICDAR-POD 2017

Training parameters	Value
Image Min/Max Dim	255
Train RoIs Per Image	32
Learning Rate	0.001
Learning Momentum	0.9
Epochs	100
Steps per epoch	1800
Detection Min Confidence	0.7
Detection NMS threshold	0.3

TABLE III: Summary of Training parameters used for implementing the DOD model.

competition [20]. The performances have been compared with the mean Average Precision(mAP) and average F1-score as used in the competition as shown in Table IV.

For the PubLayNet dataset, we used our model to train and evaluate categorically with the 5 classes and get the AP scores for both object detection and instance segmentation using the mask RCNN model. It is important to note that we have proposed the first baseline approach successfully for instance segmentation [54] with our mask RCNN model. As this dataset is relatively new, there is not enough literature to be compared in this case. We have shown the results we obtained with the proposed Mask RCNN model on both object detection and instance segmentation tasks with category based AP scores in Table VI.

4) *Experiments with cross-dataset evaluation:* In this experiment setup, we conducted a cross dataset evaluation between the three datasets used in our study. We introduce the modified ICDAR-RDCL-2019 dataset after data augmentation as one of the source datasets for training. Table V highlights that we have evaluated our model results on the ICDAR-POD-2017 dataset. We have taken an initialized pre-trained COCO model as a baseline and mix and matched by fine-tuning with the PubLayNet and RDCL datasets which have a distinct difference in layout as magazine articles are different when compared to scientific articles that are taken from PubMed Central [58]. Fine tuning for a different domain actually helps us to see how well the model generalizes from the source domain to the target domain. It also provides a substantial insight on how much knowledge is getting transferred in this case study.

Methods	Category: AP			mAP	Category: F1 score			
	Table	Fig.	Eqn.		Table	Fig.	Eqn.	F1(avg.)
NLPR-PAL	0.911	0.805	0.816	0.844	0.951	0.898	0.902	0.917
HustVision	0.796	0.656	0.293	0.582	0.115	0.132	0.042	0.096
VisInt	0.795	0.565	0.117	0.492	0.826	0.643	0.241	0.570
FastDetectors	0.884	0.365	0.427	0.559	0.896	0.616	0.639	0.717
Faster-RCNN (proposed)	0.901	0.897	0.712	0.836	0.951	0.821	0.881	0.884
Mask-RCNN (proposed)	0.932	0.898	0.858	0.896	0.978	0.911	0.913	0.934

TABLE IV: Comparison with State-of-the-art based on ICDAR-POD-2017 dataset.

5) *Ablation Study:* We conducted an ablation study on the basis of the significance of Feature Pyramid Networks(FPNs) to our model architecture. Studies conducted on the PubLayNet and ICDAR-POD-2017 dataset clearly highlights the significance of using them for our model framework. Results are clearly illustrated as shown in Table VII.

D. Experimental setup for Document Layout Generation

We used 70 percent of the graph samples from the RVLCDIP invoices subset for training and the rest 30 percent of the samples have been used for testing.

Category	Training set	Faster-RCNN(AP)	Masked RCNN(AP)
Table	COCO(tr)	0.721	0.733
	COCO(tr)+PubLayNet(ft)	0.801	0.796
	COCO(tr)+RDCL(ft)	0.725	0.775
Figures	COCO(tr)	0.625	0.699
	COCO(tr)+PubLayNet(ft)	0.695	0.712
	COCO(tr)+RDCL(ft)	0.632	0.654
Equations	COCO(tr)	0.702	0.716
	COCO(tr)+PubLayNet(ft)	0.751	0.798
	COCO(tr)+RDCL(ft)	0.723	0.745

TABLE V: Comparison of performances on ICDAR-POD-17 by fine tuning on Prima and PubLayNet datasets.

Category	Object detection (AP)	Instance Segmentation(AP)
Text	0.911	0.906
Title	0.823	0.804
List	0.875	0.781
Table	0.961	0.963
Figure	0.943	0.938
mAP	0.904	0.879

TABLE VI: Performance achieved by Mask RCNN on the PubLayNet dataset with Object detection and Instance Segmentation.

Model	mAP (PubLayNet)	mAP (POD-2017)
Faster RCNN(source)	0.843	0.795
Faster RCNN(with FPN)	0.871	0.836
Mask RCNN(source)	0.875	0.882
Mask RCNN(with FPN)	0.904	0.896

TABLE VII: Performance analysis of DOD model with or without FPN.

1) *Data preparation for graph representation:* In this stage, given the image of a document, we apply physical layout techniques to detect the graphical regions. Given an invoice document, we represent each detected entity corresponding to a 7-dimensional vector containing the position of the bounding boxes and the histogram of its content (numbers, alphabets or symbol). This encoded information will be used to generate a visibility graph in order to represent the structural information of the document. We consider $G = (V, E)$ to be a visibility graph. The set of edges E represent visibility relations between nodes. Two entities are said to be connected with an edge if and only if the bounding boxes are vertically or horizontally visible, i.e. a straight horizontal or vertical line can be traced between the bounding box of two entities without crossing any other. Also, long edges covering more than a quarter of the page height are discarded. An example of a visibility graph sample with corresponding node embedding is shown in Figure 7.

2) *Training setup for Graph Recurrent Neural Network:* Once the document has been processed and visibility graph has been generated, we feed them to our Graph Recurrent Neural Network (GRNN) model framework with the 7-dimensional node input space to get projected to a higher order space encoding with individual node features preserving the structural content information of the document. The graph-level RNN used in our work uses 4 layered GRU with 128 dimensional hidden state. To output the adjacency vector prediction, the edge-level RNN uses 4 layered GRU cells with 16 hidden dimensional state. To get the predicted adjacency vector in the output, the edge-level RNN maps the 16 dimensional hidden state to a 8 dimensional vector through a MLP and ReLU activation, then another MLP maps the vector to a scalar with sigmoid activation. We initialize the the edge-level RNN by the output of the graph-level RNN when generating the start of sequences S_{i-1}^{π} . We use the highest layer hidden state of the graph-level RNN to initialize with a linear layer to match the dimensionality. During the training time, ground truth has been used rather than the model's own predictions. During the inference time, the model is allowed to use its own predicted graph samples at each time step to generate a graph. The Adam Optimizer has been used been used for minibatch size of 32. We set the learning rate to be 0.001 which is decayed by 0.2 at every 100th epoch in all experiments.

3) *Experiments on administrative documents:* Experiments on the subset of administrative document (invoices) taken from RVL-CDIP has been conducted and we report the first baseline for document layout generation using a Graph Neural Network(GNN) framework. The qualitative and quantitative result analysis has been covered in the next Results and Discussions section.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section we have provided deep insights into the experimental results we have achieved both qualitatively and quantitatively. We shall discuss them in the following sections in correspondence with the tasks we have worked in the thesis:

A. Results on Document Object Detection

Extensive experiments performed with the datasets for the DOD task has fetched us important results. They can be elucidated as follows:

- Training and evaluating our proposed DOD model on the ICDAR-POD-2017 dataset helps us to fetch state-of-the-art results compared to the existing state-of-the-art approaches submitted to the ICDAR-POD competition [20]. Our end-to-end trainable model on both Faster-RCNN and Mask-RCNN has outshone the other models like NLPR-PAL, HustVision, VisInt, FastDetectors on both mAP and F1 score metrics as shown in Table IV. We have illustrated in our results by

Fig. 7: Graph representation of an invoice with the node embeddings clearly shown on the right credited to Riba *et. al* [62].

Fig. 8: Document layout predictions on the POD dataset by the proposed Masked RCNN detector.

calculating both AP and F1 scores for the 3 categories of objects. Results show that tables are detected most accurately compared to figures and equations.

- Qualitative analysis of our experiments using the Mask RCNN based detector on the POD-2017 dataset are shown in Figure 8. The model works perfect for this task with all the categories (tables, figures, equations) clearly detected as shown by the boxes of different colours. Previous results show equations and figures may be hard to detect due to its complex structure in scientific articles and there might be a lot of false positives. But this problem is overcome in our method as shown both qualitatively and quantitatively.
- The results for training and evaluating our proposed DOD Mask RCNN based model on the new PubLayNet dataset are shown in Table VI. The mAP score has been computed in this case for all the different categories of objects(text, lists, tables, title and figure) as shown in the result table. We have also presented instance segmentation baseline results on this dataset using the Mask-RCNN who is a new contribution. Very high AP scores have been obtained for tables and figures which is very encouraging. The AP scores for instance segmentation are also high for both of these categories. The title category seems to be the weakest one because of the different variety of ways they are presented in documents and can be improved further. On the other hand, titles often get identified with text category, so it is quite challenging.
- Qualitative results on the training and evaluation of our model on the PubLayNet dataset has been illustrated in Figure 9. Detection of the predicted document layouts with high confidence scores clearly indicate how it good it performs for

Fig. 9: Qualitative analysis on the PubLayNet dataset by the proposed Masked RCNN detector

parsing layout of scientific articles. Looking at the 6th example case in Figure 9 we notice that there is some section of text layout which gets undetected. This is probably due to the confusion in category between lists and title.

- Also an interesting study was conducted based on domain adaptation and transfer by pre-training and fine tuning on a source dataset and then evaluating on a different dataset. Table V clearly illustrates the usage of COCO pre-trained models with fine tuning on PubLayNet and then on the modified ICDAR-RDCL-2019 dataset and get their corresponding evaluated AP scores on the ICDAR-POD-2017 dataset. Fine-tuning on the PubLayNet dataset gets the best results for all the 3 object categories. Intuitively we can improve the performance of the cross-domain evaluation by adding techniques to learn more domain invariant features, which is a future scope of our work.

B. Results on Document Layout Generation

As illustrated in Figure 10, we illustrate some of the qualitative results with the document graphs that we generated from our proposed GRNN model. The visualizations of the graph samples suggest that the model more or less learns to preserve both syntactic and semantic information of entities. Eventually, we can create synthetic samples of invoices by generating more and more graph samples and also providing them during the inference time. Since this is the first baseline approach to use graph generative models in document datasets, we could not compare the quantitative performance with state-of-the-art. But the Table VIII depicts the quantitative results we obtained for our own contributed dataset and we compared our model performance with some state-of-the-art molecule datasets. Results clearly show that there is a huge room for improvement in

Fig. 10: Generated document graph samples on the RVLCDIP dataset by the proposed GRNN model.

graph generative framework for documents when compared to benchmark molecular datasets. The 'tables' entity is a regular structured entity and our model works well for generating table classes in realistic positions. But the title, date and other entities in administrative documents do not contain uniform information about its structural relations and its quite difficult for the model to learn those semantic content. We will continue our research on the synthetic document graph generation domain to extend our master dissertation work.

Dataset	Deg.	Clus.	Orbit
Protein	0.014	0.002	0.039
Community	0.034	0.102	0.037
RVL-CDIP Invoices	0.373	0.166	0.188

TABLE VIII: Comparison of our GRNN model based on MMD scores with benchmark molecular datasets.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This dissertation has proposed an end-to-end trainable model for Document Object Detection based on Faster-RCNN and Mask-RCNN object detectors. The conducted experiments have seen the models achieve state-of-the-art results on public benchmarks, ICDAR-POD-2017 and PubLayNet. To demonstrate knowledge transfer across different domains, cross-dataset evaluation resolves the problem of large scale annotated training samples. But performances can be highly improved by adding domain invariant feature extraction modules in our model, which is added as a future scope to our work. In addition, a first baseline approach to document layout generation using GNN-based generative model have been proposed. Our approach also helps to preserve confidential document content(specially, in invoices). Also, a novel dataset has been successfully contributed to the community for layout generation task from the RVL-CDIP invoice data.

Since, there are no proper metrics for document layout generation tasks, hence we look to come up with a proper metric in future. Also, the performances for our graph generation model has huge scope for future improvement.

APPENDIX A

QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS ON OTHER DATA

Since, we didn't show quantitative analysis on ICDAR-RDCL-2019 due to high amount of discrepancy in class categories, we decided to show some qualitative results based on our proposed DOD model. Figure 11 illustrates some results on this dataset using the Faster-RCNN based model.

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(a) fig 1

(b) fig 2

(c) fig 3

Fig. 11: Examples on the ICDAR-RDCL-2019 dataset on the DOD model Faster RCNN detector.

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